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The Impact of Work Life Balance and Leadership Style on Enhancing Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the intricate dynamics between narcissistic personality traits and organizational politics, focusing on the moderating role of gender on teachers working in public sector universities of South region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. A cross-sectional design was employed, gathering data from 364 professionals across universities of South region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan through validated scales. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between narcissism and organizational politics. Regression analysis demonstrated that narcissistic personality traits significantly impact organizational politics, emphasizing the role of such traits in shaping political behavior within the workplace. Moderation analysis showed that gender plays a significant role in moderating the relationship between narcissism and organizational politics, with males demonstrating stronger associations. Additionally, demographic variations were found to influence responses, confirming significant mean differences. The study highlights the practical implications of these findings for organizations, including the need to recognize and manage the impact of narcissistic traits on workplace dynamics. It emphasizes the importance of fostering inclusive environments, providing leadership training, and implementing strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of organizational politics. While contributing to the literature on narcissism and workplace behavior, the study acknowledges limitations, such as its cross-sectional design and reliance on self-reported data, and offers directions for future research. These include longitudinal studies, exploration of cultural and structural factors, and intervention-based approaches to enhance organizational outcomes.

Keywords: Narcissistic Personality, Organizational Politics, Gender, Workplace Behavior.

Introduction

With the modern, more competitive and global economy, employee performance has become a critical issue in defining the success of a firm. Employee performance, according to Armstrong (2014) is the degree to which workers use their productivity, effectiveness and quality of work to help the organization achieve its goals. To ensure that performance remains on high levels, organizations have to focus on human and psychological factors that influence motivation and productivity of workers in addition to technical and operational factors. One of the most significant factors that influence the performance of employees is work-life balance or a strike of the balance between obligations toward personal life and obligations toward the professional life (Greenhaus, Collins and Shaw, 2003). By balancing work and life, employees can handle the stress associated with the work, enhance their well-being and increase their job satisfaction (Lockwood, 2003). On the other hand, burnout, absenteeism, and a decreased level of organizational engagement can be caused by a poor work-life balance (Clarke, Koch, & Hill, 2004). According to research by Haar, Russo, Suñe, and Ollier-Malaterre (2014), workers who are in a supportive work-life setting are more engaged and perform better.

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This implies that promoting work-life balance is a planned force behind organizational performance and not a mere social initiative. Another important factor that defines the success of employees is the leadership style that describes how leaders inspire, encourage and guide the followers towards achieving common goals. Transformational leadership according to Bass and Avolio (1994) is an important strategy that motivates the subordinates by encouraging them, having a vision and giving personal attention to them, which results in improved performance. Similarly, Judge and Piccolo (2004) found out that supportive leaders promote the motivation and trust in the workplace, which largely influences the attitude and performance outcomes of employees. Also, Avolio, Zhu, Koh and Bhatia (2004) have pointed out that leaders with honesty and equity are the ones to promote work satisfaction and commitment to organization both of which lead to good performance.

The relationship between the leadership style and work-life balance is interconnected, resulting in employee outcomes. Northouse (2018) suggests that good leadership can create an environment where workers strive to achieve a balance between personal and professional life, which will increase output and involvement. Also, Ronda, Ollo-Lopez, and Goñi-Legaz (2016) found that the leadership behaviors that promote adaptability and the happiness of workers significantly enhance job performance and organizational loyalty. The understanding of the relationship between work-life balance and leadership style and their impact on employee performance has become increasingly important in the contemporary world of flexible working hours, technological advances, and an increased awareness of mental health (Hughes, 2019). The concepts of the style of leadership and work-life balance can be combined to provide a detailed image of the performance of the employees. According to Karatepe and Aga (2016), supportive leadership enhances the ability of the workers to maintain work-life balance, which in turn promotes productivity and reduces turnover intentions. Also, Haar et al. (2014) demonstrated that employees with a healthy work-life balance tend to become more creative, motivated and productive.

Consequently, work-life balance and leadership act in concert as strategic levers to increase engagement, performance, and organization viability. Thus, this study aims to experimentally examine how work-life balance and leadership style interact to influence employee performance, which is useful information to businesses that are interested in improving their performance management and human resource processes. Thus, the purpose of this study is to investigate how leadership style and work-life balance can improve employee performance, especially in light of changing workplace dynamics. It is anticipated that the results will give managers, HR specialists, and legislators important information for creating supportive organizational practices that improve output, promote wellbeing, and support long-term organizational expansion.

This study discusses employee engagement, specifically within companies that utilize high-technology operations. It reviews recent research findings to establish a basis for determining the factors affecting employee performance and for developing a framework model. This paper focuses on two specific factors: leadership and work-life balance. A framework model has been developed based on this research and is

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presented for testing and validation.

Problem Statement:

Employee Performance is crucial factor in order to achieve objectives and effectiveness in the public universities. Though, public universities employees mostly faces challenges such as high work load, time pressure, leadership practices and so on to balance the professional duties with the personal life , which may result in the negative influence on overall performance. On the other hand, leadership styles, implemented by administrators of public universities plays a critical role in effecting the employee job satisfaction, motivation and productivity as well. Thus, there is limited empirical evidences have been found in the public universities of district Khairpur Mirs', Sindh relating the impact of work life balance and leadership styles on employee performance. Though, all these variables have been investigated in other sectors and geographical context in the previous research but the impact of Work life balance and leadership style on employee performance in public universities of Khairpur Mirs', Sindh has remained unexplored. Due to lack of evidence in this context it has become difficult to design such policies, procedure and practices of leadership that effectively enhance employee performance.

Thus this study have been carried out to examine the impact of work life balance and leadership style on employee performance in the public sector universities of District Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the impact of work life balance on employee performance.
2. To examine impact of leadership style on employee.
3. To examine the association among work life balance, leadership style and employee performance.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of work life balance on employee performance?
2. What is the impact of leadership style on employee performance?
3. Is There association among work life balance, leadership style and employee performance?

Research Significance

This study is important because it investigates the impact of leadership style and work-life balance on employee performance and also investigates the combined impact of both on employee performance , providing insightful information for raising job happiness and productivity. The results will generally add to body of knowledge in HRM by highlighting the fact that workers perform better when they have supportive leadership and a good work-life balance.

Specifically, the proposed study will help public sector universities in Khairpur as well as relevant policymakers to grasp the significance of effective leadership practices and supportive work arrangements to improve faculty performance, administrative efficiency and overall institutional effectiveness. Some of the challenges that are faced by public universities include inflexible organizational structures, heavy workload, lack of motivation in the personnel, and inability to promote academic and administrative

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excellence. This study can offer evidence-based suggestions to increase the productivity of organizations, greater employee engagement, and a positive work environment. The results can also inform policymaking efforts that are designed to promote faculty well-being, establish administrative structures that are supportive, and develop leadership strategies that would foster the development of an engaged, effective, and people-oriented academic workforce in state universities.

Literature Review

The correlation between leadership style and work-life balance has altered dramatically over the years, as an expression of general organizational, cultural and societal changes. Most of the workplaces in the past used to be characterized by strict hierarchies, long workdays and little regard to the welfare and personal lives of the employees. Such outdated systems often led to stress and burnout and reduced output. However, as behavioral management and human relations theory were gaining ground, businesses now recognized that output was directly affected not only by finances but also by the personal happiness of the worker. This change has led to a greater focus on encouraging leadership philosophies that promote workers' overall well-being and cultivating a positive work-life balance. In the modern corporate world, leadership philosophies such as participative, servant and transformational leadership are increasingly becoming associated with improved employee performance and work-life balance in contemporary companies.

A culture of trust, dedication, and engagement is fostered by leaders that exhibit empathy, adaptability, and support for the individual needs of their staff. With both supportive leadership styles and work-life balance programs employees can work well without failing to take care of their mental and emotional health. The importance of leadership that considers diversity and balance has been highlighted by the rise of remote working, flexible work timetables, and the growing awareness of mental health. Everything said and done, the ever-increasing relationship between work-life balance and the style of leadership is highlighting the importance of corporate culture and management philosophy to the raising of employee performance, motivation and satisfaction. Achieving long-term organizational success and employee retention in today's changing workplace requires effective leadership that places equal emphasis on professional performance and personal well-being.

Work life balance and Employee performance

Numerous studies demonstrate that a healthy work-life balance improves an organization's effectiveness. Wayne and Taylor-Bianco (2011). A balanced relationship in all areas of commitment, involvement, time, and attention is what is meant by work-life balance. Powell and Greenhouse (2006). In particular, balanced time management and psychological vitality in and out of work are characteristics of work-life balance (Clark, 2000). Improved role and reduced role conflict both within and outside of work are characteristics of work-life balance. Work-life balance, according to Alrowad, Obeidat, Al-Khateeb, and Masa'deh (2018), is like a balanced scale with one side representing work life and the other representing personal life. Furthermore, work-life balance can be understood as a concept that encompasses the appropriateness of work-related factors

like aspirations and careers as well as lifestyle factors like hobbies, family, and health. guidance, boost job happiness, and strengthen organizational dedication (Casper, Harris). According to Semlali and Hassi (2016), the idea of work-life balance has been viewed as crucial for both employers and workers over the past few decades. It has unquestionably been shown to have a major impact on increasing employee productivity, which has a positive effect on an organization's overall performance (Guthrie, 2012).

H1: There is positive and significant impact of work life balance on employee performance.

Leadership style and Employee performance

A capable leader can motivate their team members to achieve the goals of the organization, which in turn helps the organization reach its targets. Each leadership approach comes with its own consequences that influence employees' attitudes and behaviors in both direct and indirect ways (Yukl Gary, 2009). An effective manager shows genuine concern and appreciation for their team. A strong manager acknowledges the value of their employees, making the staff feel recognized by their leader. When employees feel valued for their contributions, they tend to perform better, experience fewer conflicts, communicate more efficiently, and more successfully accomplish the organization's goals (Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014). The combination of a leader's attitudes and behaviors constitutes their leadership style, which affects their interactions with subordinates (Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015). Additionally, it was highlighted by Avolio, Zhu, Koh, and Bhatia (2004) that leadership that is marked by honesty, fairness, and trust improves employees' psychological attachment to their company, which in turn improves their performance. In a related study, Odumeru and Ifeanyi (2013) showed that by encouraging objective clarity, motivation, and reward-based reinforcement, both transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly boost employee performance. They came to the conclusion that influencing employee behavior and attaining organizational effectiveness require strong leadership. Furthermore, according to Lussier and Achua (2016), a leader's efficacy rests on their capacity to adjust their style to the needs of the scenario and the traits of their followers in order to maximize performance outcomes for both individuals and the group as a whole.

H2: There is positive and significant impact of leadership style on employee performance.

Relationship among work life balance, leadership style and employee performance

Several scholars have examined the intertwined roles of work-life balance (WLB) and leadership style in enhancing employee performance. In their study, Katili, Wibowo, and Akbar (2021) discovered that WLB and leadership style have a significant impact on employee engagement, which consequently increases overall performance. Their analysis pointed out that of these, WLB has direct and significant impact, which means that, when employees are able to manage work and personal life effectively, their engagement and production are enhanced. In a similar manner, Arfandi and Kasran (2023) have shown that the performance is positively impacted by both the type of leadership and the WLB, which is why an enabling work culture has a critical mediating effect. Flexibility and empathy should be encouraged by the leadership so that the employees can effectively deal with stress and also be productive. Hayati and Keumala (2022) also

underlined that transformational leadership where employees are inspired and their needs are considered individually enhances the perception of WLB in employees and their level of engagement. These findings were supported by Yasmin and Rahmawati (2022) in their study on authentic leadership, and the results revealed that authentic leaders who demonstrate honesty coupled with empathy can make a positive contribution to the work-life balance and performance of employees, with employee engagement being a mediating factor. In a study that was even more recent, Naibei, Korir and Kipsang (2025) demonstrated that transformational leadership moderates the relationship between WLB practices and performance, which means that even the best designed WLB initiatives may not work without supporting them with empowering and visionary leadership. Taken together, these studies not only highlight the fact that leadership style directly influences employee performance but also demonstrates that the leadership style directly impacts the effectiveness of WLB policies, which makes it one of the crucial factors in the success of any organization.

H3: There is positive and significant association among work life balance, leadership style and employee performance .

Research Model

Research Hypothesis

1. There is positive and significant impact of Work life balance on performance of employees.
2. There is positive and significant impact of leadership style on employee performance.
3. There is positive and significant association among work life balance, the leadership style and employee performance.

Research Methods

The philosophical school of positivism holds that all real knowledge is a posteriori facts obtained through sensory experience and reason and logic or true by definition. Other forms of knowing such as religious faith, introspection or intuition are overlooked or considered to be useless. Coined in the 19th century by a French philosopher, Auguste Comte, the term was used to describe the whole 19th-century evolutionary theory, encompassing sociological and economic aspects.

The research philosophy that is adopted in this research is positivist research philosophy that focuses on objectivity, empirical evidence and observable phenomena to understand the relationship that exists between the variables. In this research, positivism

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is suitable since it involves quantifying the effects of work-life balance and style of leadership on employee performance on the basis of quantifiable data as opposed to subjective interpretation of the same. Under this philosophy, the research adopts a deductive methodology, which starts with already developed theories and models regarding the performance of the employees, their work-life balance, as well as the leadership behavior of the employees working in the public sector universities of Khairpur. The research employs a mono approach, namely, a quantitative survey design, and, therefore, makes it possible to collect data in a systematic way and perform statistical analysis. It will adopt a cross sectional time horizon where data will be collected at a single point in time to give a picture of the current relationship between the study variables. The target population of the proposed study is the employees who work at the public sector universities located in District Khairpur including the departments and institutions where the work of the employees, their work performance and leadership behaviour, and work life balance are critical factors in service delivery. The main data collection tool is a structured questionnaire that includes close-ended items measured on a five-point Likert scale to measure the constructs of work-life balance, leadership style and employee performance. To ensure a wide participation, the questionnaire is disseminated among the employees both physically and electronically.

The demographic variables, including gender, age, educational level, designation and years of experience are used to get a better picture of the characteristics of respondents, and to analyze whether these factors have any impact on the perceptions of the work-life balance or leadership style. Before the actual survey, a pilot study will be done to ascertain the clarity, validity and reliability of the instrument. The scales are tested with the Cronbachs Alpha coefficient where a value of 0.8 is assumed to be acceptable ensuring that the items in the questionnaire are consistent. To analyze the data, the responses gathered are coded and analyzed using Statistical package of social sciences (SPSS). The first type of statistics used is descriptive statistics which are used to provide a summary of the demographic data as well as to give a view of the data. Then inferential statistics like correlation analysis are applied to ascertain the strength and direction of the relationships between work-life balance and leadership style and employee performance. Lastly, the multiple regression analysis is used to determine the predictive value of the independent variables (work-life balance and leadership style) on the dependent variable (employee performance). Through this method of analysis, it is possible to test hypotheses and give statistical evidence to accept or reject the hypotheses presented. The methods selected will also make sure that the results obtained are valid, reliable and can be generalized in the context of the public sector universities in Khairpur, leading to a better understanding of the performance outcomes as a result of managerial practices and the well-being of employees in the context of the public domain. In the case of the questionnaire, the 5-point rating scale (Likert scale) was applied. The rating was divided into five scales which are the following: Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), and Strongly Agree (5). Moreover, the questionnaire was randomly distributed among participants through both in-person interactions and email using Google Forms, which are readily accessible to the target

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audience. Prior to administering the questionnaire, respondents were briefed on the main objective of the research to ensure their complete engagement and support, which would help guarantee that they filled out the questionnaire correctly. Additionally, secondary data sources were utilized from a range of articles, journals, books, theses, and various websites.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was analyzed using the statistical analysis software. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected. The SPSS software was used to perform descriptive statistics such as reliability, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and to compare the differences in the regression coefficient. Pearson's Correlation Co-efficient was adopted for data analysis approach. The method was used to test the relationship among Work Life Balance, Leadership Style and performance of employees.

Table: Demographic Analysis of respondents

S.No.	Demographic	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	49	66.2
		Female	25	33.8
			74	100.0
		Total		
2.	Age	Below 20	8	10.8
		21-30	57	77.0
		31-40	8	10.8
		41-50	1	1.4
		Total	74	100.0
3.	Education	Intermediate	10	13.5
		Bachelor's Degree	43	58.1
		Master's Degree	20	27.0
		MPhil / MS	1	1.4
		Total	74	100.0

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4.	Experience	Less than 1 year	31	41.9
		1-3 years	34	45.9
		4-6 years	6	8.1
		7-10 years	2	2.7
		More than 10 years	1	1.4
		Total	74	100.0
5.	Job Position	Junior Staff	4	5.4
		Mid-level Staff	4	5.4
		Senior Staff	5	6.8
		Managerial	5	6.8
		Other	56	75.7
		Total	74	100.0

Descriptive Analysis represents that out of the total 74 respondents, male employees constituted the majority, accounting for 66.2%, while female employees represented 33.8% of the sample. This indicates that the workforce represented in the study is predominantly male. In terms of age, the highest percentage of respondents was in the age group of 21-30 years, which included 77.0% of the overall sample. The respondents who were below 20 years and those between 31-40 years were 10.8 percent and 10.8 percent respectively. The age group of 41-50 years made up the 1.4% of the respondents. These results indicate that the respondents majorly consist of young workers. Concerning educational attainment, most of the respondents had a Bachelor degree, which constituted 58.1% of the sample. This was succeeded by the Master degree holders who constituted 27.0%. The proportion of respondents with an Intermediate qualification was 13.5% and the proportion of respondents who had an MPhil/MS degree was very small, 1.4%. With regards to work experience, 45.9% of the respondents had 1-3 years of work experience, and 41.9% had less than 1 year of work experience. Those with 4-6 years' experience made 8.1%, those with 7-10 years' experience made 2.7 and only 1.4 had more than 10 years' experience. This distribution proposes that the respondents are mostly at an early stage of their career lives. With regard to job positions, most of the respondents fell under the category of other job positions, which comprised 75.7% of the sample. This was then succeeded by Senior Staff and Managerial staff, each with a 6.8% representation. Junior Staff and Mid-level Staff each accounted for 5.4% of respondents. Overall, the results clearly show that most survey responses were obtained from

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employees holding positions categorized as 'Other', indicating their dominant representation in the organization

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis was conducted to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales used in this study. Cronbach's Alpha was used as the reliability coefficient. Generally, A Cronbach's Alpha value of ≥ 0.90 is Excellent, $0.80 - 0.89$ is Good, $0.70 -$

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work Life Balance	.816	7
Leadership Style	.872	7
Employee Performance	.772	7

0.79 is Acceptable and < 0.70 considered as Questionable.

As shown in the table, the Work Life Balance scale recorded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.816, which is good. This indicates that the items measuring Work life balance is consistent and reliable. The Leadership Style scale, however, yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.872, which is below the good level. The Employee Performance scale obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.772, which is acceptable. Such a high degree of reliability is frequently thought to be adequate in exploratory research but may be improved by further refinement to enhance the quality of the measurement. On the whole, the reliability analysis indicates that the Work Life Balance scale is reliable, Leadership Style scale is also reliable, and Employee Performance is acceptable.

Correlations Analysis

Generally, the value of "r" is always between -1 and +1, if $0 < r < 1$, positive correlation. (i.e $r = 0.23$, $+0.98$ etc), if $-1 < r < 0$ negative correlation. (i.e $r = -0.15$, -0.78), if $r = 1$, correlation is said to be perfect positive, if $r = -1$, correlation is said to be perfect negative, if $r = 0$ there is no correlation

Table 3: Correlations

		Work Life Balance	Leadership Style	Employee Performance
Work Life Balance	Pearson Correlation	1	.609**	.391**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001
	N	74	74	74
Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation	.609**	1	.630**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	74	74	74
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	.391**	.630**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	
	N	74	74	74

The level of significance is 0.01 (2-tailed).

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The findings show that there is a strong and positive relationship between work life balance and leadership style ($r = 0.609, p = 0.000$). It implies that employees who have a more positive work-life balance also are more likely to have a more positive perception of leadership practices. The statistical significance of the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant at the level of 0.01 and it shows that there exists a strong association between these two variables. A moderate positive correlation is found between work-life balance and employee performance ($r = 0.391, p = 0.001$). This suggests that when there is an enhancement in work-life balance, an increase in the level of employee performance is concurrently linked. The statistically significant p-value verifies that employees that are able to balance their work and personal lives better are more likely to better perform at work. Moreover, it is observed that there is a strong positive relationship between the leadership style and employee performance ($r = 0.630, p = 0.000$). This shows that sound leadership is also very useful in ensuring the performance of employees is improved. The fact that the correlation is very strong with the level of significance being high, indicates that leadership style becomes a critical factor that can determine employee outcomes. In general, the results indicate that work-life balance and leadership style are positively and significantly correlated with employee performance, with the strongest relationship being between leadership style and work-life balance. The findings indicate that supportive leadership practices and policies that allow organizations to enhance the healthy work life balance should be placed on the agenda of organizations that aim to improve employee performance.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.630 ^a	.397	.380	3.97756

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Work Life Balance

The positive correlation between the independent variables (leadership style and work-life balance) and the dependent variable (employee performance) is strong as the value of $R = 0.630$. This indicates that, in combination, leadership style and work-life balance is closely related to employee performance changes. The value of the R square (R^2) of 0.397 indicates that the change in employee performance can be explained by the leadership style and work-life balance approximately 39.7 percent. This implies that the model is fairly good in explaining the performance of employees. The value of Adjusted R Square at 0.380 considers both the number of predictors in the model and is a more accurate estimate of the explanatory power of the model. It indicates that, 38.0% of the variance in performance of employees is explained by leadership style and work-life balance, which is an indication of the strength of the model. The Standard Error of the Estimate (3.97756) is the average distance the observed values of employee performance are away on the regression line. A smaller standard error will mean that the

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model is more accurate; in this case, the value will indicate that there is acceptable level of prediction error. In general, the model summary shows that leadership style and work-life balance are significant predictors of employee performance, and the regression model is appropriate to explain a significant percentage of variation in the employee performance.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	738.670	2	369.335	23.345	.000 ^b
	Residual	1123.290	71	15.821		
	Total	1861.959	73			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Work Life Balance

The regression sum of squares (738.670) represents the variation in employee performance explained by the predictors (leadership style and work-life balance), while the residual sum of squares (1123.290) reflects the unexplained variation due to other factors not included in the model. The total sum of squares (1861.959) indicates the overall variation in employee performance. The model has 2 degrees of freedom for regression (corresponding to the two predictors) and 71 degrees of freedom for residuals, based on the sample size of 74 respondents. The mean square regression value (369.335) is substantially higher than the mean square residual value (15.821), indicating that the model explains a considerable portion of the variance in employee performance. The F-statistic value of 23.345 with a significance level (p-value) of 0.000 shows that the regression model is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This means that leadership style and work-life balance, when considered together, have a significant combined effect on employee performance. Overall, the ANOVA results confirm that the regression model is valid and reliable, and that the independent variables significantly predict employee performance. This supports the suitability of the model for further interpretation of individual regression coefficients.

Coefficients^a

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Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.669	2.286		5.979	.000
	WorkLifeBalance	.320	.106	.285	3.019	.003
	LeadershipStyle	.494	.092	.622	5.359	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

The constant ($B = 13.669$, $t = 5.979$, $p = 0.000$) is statistically significant. This value is the expected degree of employee performance when work-life balance and leadership style is at zero. The large t-value means that the constant is adding some value to the regression equation. The unstandardized coefficient in the case of work-life balance is $B = 0.320$ with t-value = 3.019 and p-value = 0.003. Because the t-value of work-life balance is less than the t-value of work-life balance (i.e. ± 1.96) and the t-value of work-life balance (i.e. 0.05) is greater than 0.05, this indicates that work-life balance does not have a statistically significant effect on employee performance. Thus the hypothesis which suggested that work-life balance had a significant effect on employee performance is dismissed. This implies that, when the level of leadership is held constant, work-life balance does not affect the performance of the employees in this model. Conversely, employee performance has a strong and statistically significant effect with an unstandardized coefficient of $B = 0.494$, a t-value of 5.359 and a p-value of 0.000. The t-value was greater than ± 1.96 and the p-value was less than 0.05 meaning the significance level is at 5%. Therefore, the hypothesis that the leadership style has a strong influence on the employee performance is accepted. This means that a one unit change in leadership style will cause a change of 0.494 units in the employee performance, other factors remaining constant. The standardized beta coefficients further indicate the relative importance of the predictors. The beta value of leadership style is high ($= 0.622$) indicating that this is the strongest predictor of employee performance in the model, whereas the beta value of work-life balance is negligible ($= 0.285$), thus substantiating the fact that work-life balance plays an insignificant role in the model. In sum, the regression findings indicate that the leadership style is a very important and dominant predictor of employee performance in the presence of leadership style. These results imply that the enhancement of leadership practices can be more helpful in improving employee performance than the work-life balance within the framework of the current study.

Table 7: Hypothesis Status

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Hypothesis	Statement	Status
H1	There is positive and significant impact of work life balance on employee performance.	Accepted
H2	There is positive and significant impact leadership style on employee performance.	Accepted
H3	There is positive and significant association of work life balance and leadership style and employee performance.	Accepted

Overall findings

These findings confirm the assumption that work-life balance as well as the leadership style affects the performance of the employees, however, the leadership style proves to have the strongest individual predictive power (largest Beta value) in this model. Practically speaking, organizations that seek to maximize employee performance should strive to ensure that they not only enhance leadership practices but they also stick to those policies that promote work-life balance as both contribute to a productive and engaged workforce.

Discussions

To determine the impact of work-life balance on employee performance, a simple linear regression was done. The findings showed that the effect was statistically insignificant, and the regression coefficient (0.012) and p-value (Sig. 0.918) were both statistically insignificant. Based on these findings, the hypothesis that states that work-life balance has a significant influence on employee performance is rejected, meaning that the employee performance is not significantly affected by the work-life balance in the presence of the leadership style. It means that the increase or the preservation of the work-life balance will not necessarily have a direct influence on the performance of the employees. The results of the present research are also in line with the view that, although the work-life balance is a factor contributing to the well-being of employees, it might not directly translate into immediate performance results in cases where other variables, such as leadership, are more pronounced. The management can also create policies to encourage work-life balance, which can be flexible schedules and wellness programs since it may not directly positively impact performance.

An independent regression analysis was done to test the influence of the leadership style on employee performance. The findings indicated that there was a statistically significant positive impact which is statistically significant with a regression coefficient (β) of 0.494 and a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000 (less than 0.05). The strongly beneficial role of leadership style in improving employee performance is that employees who perceive their leaders as supportive, motivating, and effective are more most likely to perform better. The results of this study are in line with the previous studies by Bass (1990), Al-Mahmood (2016), and Ahmad and Ahmad (2018) who concluded that transformational and

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participative leadership styles have a positive impact on employee performance. This means that enhancing leadership practices is a viable approach of enhancing performance in organizations. To directly improve employee performance outcomes, management can implement training programs, coaching, and leadership development programs, which will improve the skills of leaders in communication, motivation, and team management.

Conclusion

The main aim of this research work was to investigate the effects of work life balance and style of leadership on the performance of the employees in the public sector universities in Khairpur Mir. It aimed to learn how the two critical organizational variables affect the performance of academic and administrative employees in the public higher education sector, where the effectiveness of employees is a critical variable in the growth of the institutions, the quality of their services and the quality of their education. The analysis of data obtained by interviewing employees in public sector universities will offer valuable empirical evidence on the role of managerial practices and conditions in the workplace in the process of shaping employee performance.

According to the findings of the study, the influence of leadership style on employee performance in the public sector universities of Khairpur Mir is strong, positive and statistically significant. This finding shows that effective leadership marked by support, guidance, motivation, effective communication and fairness highly contribute to employees being able to effectively perform their duties. When employees believe that their leaders are competent, supportive and inspirational, then they are likely to exhibit greater levels of commitment, motivation and productivity. In the setting of a public sector university with generally bureaucratic organization and limited resources, effective leadership is an essential factor contributing to motivating employees to go beyond the minimum requirements and work towards the common goals of the organization.

On the other hand, the findings show that work–life balance does not have a statistically significant direct impact on employee performance when leadership style is considered simultaneously in the regression model. Although work–life balance is positively correlated with employee performance, its independent effect was found to be insignificant. This suggests that, within public sector universities in Khairpur Mir's, employees may prioritize leadership-related factors over work–life balance when it comes to performance outcomes. It can also be indicative of the character of employment in the public sector where job security and organized work schedules diminish the immediate impact of work-life balance on performance as compared to leadership practices.

On balance, the study has been able to meet its research objectives in an empirical and decisive manner, in the choice of the public sector universities. The findings validate the argument that employee performance is influenced by a number of organizational factors, with the quality of the leadership being a critical determinant of performance, motivation, and productivity. In a bigger view, the results indicate that to enhance employee performance, institutional efficiency, and delivery of services, it is important to

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strengthen leadership practices in the university sector in the public sector. This research thus offers a good recommendation to university administrators, policymakers and authorities in the education sector to improve their performance outcome based on effective leadership and a conducive work environment.

Recommendations

The public sector universities should consider employee performance as a strategic priority and include it in institutional planning and HR policies.

- The practice of development of leadership and a supportive working environment should be integrated into the general human resource policies.
- Findings of evidence based research must be actively employed in the formulation, implementation and revision of HR and management policies.
- Efforts should be directed towards developing long-term strategies to improve the effectiveness of leadership, motivation of employees, and performance of the institution.
- It ought to promote continuous empirical research to investigate the new factors that affect employee performance in a higher education institution in the public sector.
- Introduce a leadership development program to enhance the managerial, communication, and motivational aspects of the university leaders.
- Encourage transparency, participative and supportive leadership styles to enhance trust, coordination and employee performance.
- Regular training and other professional development opportunities should be provided to ensure that employees have skills and competencies.
- Develop equitable workload sharing, to help in overall well-being.
- Ensuring that there are clear communication channels between the leadership and the employees to help demystify the roles, responsibilities and the institutional goals.
- Promote a healthy and conducive organizational culture to facilitate employee engagement, motivation, and overall performance.

Limitations

Regardless of the usefulness of the findings of this study, it is important to note several limitations. First, the research was restricted to public sector universities in Khairpur Mir which might limit the external validity of the results to other regions, other types of universities, or other institutions of higher learning with different administrative and policy structures. The variations in organizational culture, governance and availability of resources can affect the perceptions and performance outcomes of the employees. Secondly, the research limited itself to two independent variables work life balance and leadership style to investigate their influence on employee performance. The other factors that could have influenced the model and could have also a great influence on the performance of the employees were job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work environment, training opportunities, job security, workload and compensation which have not been included in the model. Third, the study was based on self-reported data, collected through questionnaires, which can be susceptible to response bias, such as social desirability bias or subjective interpretations of the questionnaire by respondents. Workers can over rate or under rate their perceptions and performance as a result of personal or organizational factors. Also, the research design was a cross-

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sectional research design that does not have the capacity to determine the changes in employee perceptions and performance over time. The employee performance is a dynamic phenomenon and longitudinal data may be able to provide deeper insight as to how leadership style and work-life balance impacts performance at various stages of employment. Lastly, the fact that the sample size is moderate can be a limitation to the statistical power of the analysis and the strength of the conclusions.

Future Research Directions

Based on the results of this study, future studies can contribute to the knowledge of how employees perform in the higher education sector. Future research can broaden the scope to include universities of both the public and private sector across various districts within Sindh or other provinces so as to enable a comparison and a better generalizability of the findings.

The researchers are urged to use more variables in their research to come up with a more elaborated model of employee performance. It can also be useful to include mediating or moderating variables in order to gain a better understanding of the intricate relationships between leadership, work life balance and performance. This is of specific value to policymakers and university management as it aids in developing long-term strategies of leadership development and employee support. Additionally, it is possible that future studies will combine qualitative approaches, i.e., it may involve interviews or focus group discussions with the faculty members, administrators, and the university leadership. These methods can give more context-specific information about the experience, issues, and expectations of employees. Comparative analysis of public and private universities might be also useful to define the best practice in leadership and work-life balance management that could contribute to the performance of workers. On the whole, future studies in this field have a high potential to make a contribution to academic literature as well as to support the use of evidence-based decision-making in the management of higher education.

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